

Synthesis of 3-(*N*-Arylcarbamoylmethylhydrazino)-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles as Potential Antibacterials

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Fifteen new 3-(*N*-arylcarbamoylmethylhydrazino)-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles have been synthesised and screened for antibacterial activity. Some of them are active against gram +ve and -ve bacteria like *S. aureus* and *E. coli*.

SEVERAL isatin analogues possess various biological activities¹. Further, many 3-substituted-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles and their hydrazino derivatives exhibit biological activities². 1,2,4-Triazines are associated with diverse pharmacological activities³. *N*-Chloroacetyl derivatives of different substituted-anilines have also been reported to exhibit wide spectrum biological activities. With this view it was thought of interest to synthesise various 3-(*N*-arylcarbamoylmethylhydrazino)-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles by condensing 3-hydrazino-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole and chloroacetylated substituted anilines in alcohol (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analysis, counter synthesis, mixed melting points and infrared spectrum (KBr) taken on a Beckmann 20 spectrophotometer. The ir spectra of the compounds showed characteristic bands at 3 325–2 960 (NH), 1 560 (C=N) and 1 530 cm⁻¹ (N=N).

3-Hydrazino-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole: A mixture of isatin (0.5 mol), thiosemicarbazide (0.55 mol) and potassium carbonate (0.75 mol) in water (200 ml) was refluxed to yield 1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole-3-thione⁴, which were recrystallised

from a suitable solvent. Subsequently, 1,2,4-triazinoindole-3-thione (0.4 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (99%) were refluxed in equimolar proportions for 4–5 h and the resulting solid was washed with water to give 3-hydrazino-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles, which were purified by recrystallisation from DMF, (75%).

***N*-Chloroacetyl anilines:** *N*-Chloroacetyl derivatives of different substituted-anilines were prepared by the reported method⁵.

3-(*N*-Arylcarbamoylmethylhydrazino)-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles: A mixture of 3-hydrazino-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole (0.01 mol) and α -chloroacetanilide (0.01 mol) in ethanol was refluxed for 3–4 h. Excess of solvent was then distilled off and the solid which separated out on cooling was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS*

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₇ O	68	69
2.	2.Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₇ O	90	69
3.	3.Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₇ O	115	67
4.	4.Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₇ O	164	68
5.	2.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₃	75	66
6.	3.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₃	140	62
7.	4.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₃	95	63
8.	2.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₂	70	66
9.	3.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₂	101	63
10.	4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₂	144	65
11.	2.OC ₂ H ₅ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₂	140	62
12.	4.OC ₂ H ₅ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₂	170	64
13.	2.OH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₇ O	120	65
14.	3.OH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₇ O	79	68
15.	4.OH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₇ O	150	69

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Pharmacological screening: The indole derivatives were tested for antibacterial activity by cup-plate⁶ method using a species of gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus* and species of gram-negative bacteria *E. coli*. The testing was carried out in DMF solution at a concentration of 10 μ ml⁻¹. The zones of inhibition of the test solution (0.5 mg) were recorded.

Out of fifteen compounds five were found to be active against *S. aureus* and three against *E. coli*, compounds having *m*-chloro, *m*-nitro and *p*-nitro substitution to phenyl ring were active against both the species while *o*-CH₃ and *m*-CH₃ substituted compounds being active against only *S. aureus*. The presence of halogens, generally increases both the useful and toxic properties while the presence of nitro group in aromatic compounds, generally increases the toxicity, but it can be decreased by introducing some other groups. Here, we studied *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-positions of chloro, nitro, methyl, methoxy, etc. groups. Out of them, 3-chloro, 3-nitro and 4-nitro derivatives of the parent compounds showed activity against both the species.

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